

Thus, although by the mid-1970's the original stiff-strawed varieties such as TN1 and IR8 were virtually phased out

of breeding programs as direct parents, almost all the semidwarf parents that replaced them were their progeny.

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Invitation to participate in an international rice genetic survey

The increasing volume of hybridizations made in national and international rice improvement programs and the accelerated exchange of genetic material necessitate the establishment of a permanent and comprehensive record bank for the use of present and future generations of rice scientists. Some hybridization records from early breeding programs have been lost; others are relatively inaccessible. The record bank could provide information on any rice variety, including its complete genetic ancestry and the extent of its use in farmers' fields or in crosses.

Such information can help scientists to identify possible sources of resistance and to avoid the inherent dangers of genetic uniformity in the world's rice crop. IRRI invites rice scientists to collaborate in an *international rice genetic survey* to systematically gather, store, and disseminate such information. The information will be made available to all rice researchers and will help IRRI scientists and collaborators from national programs focus on problem areas considered most critical.

Information on rice varieties most widely grown by farmers, on the newest varieties released by national programs, and on elite breeding lines is also needed.

By analyzing the genetic background and traits of elite breeding lines in various programs - and of parent materials used in crosses - scientists can anticipate the types of varieties that would be released within the next few years.

We request that each breeding program send to IRRI a list of the varieties and lines described (see following) and copies of hybridization records.

MOST WIDELY GROWN VARIETIES, those grown on more than 50,000 ha within a political region or, for smaller areas, the varieties most extensively grown in farmers' fields. Include the following information:

- varietal name (or names, in some cases)
- cross (if of hybrid origin) or progenitor (if pureline selection or mutant)
- origin of variety
- plant height
- state, province, or region (political)
- main season (or seasons) grown
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture (rainfed lowland, deep water, etc.)
- growth duration (days from seed to seed)
- estimate of the area on which grown (both total number of hectares and percent of total rice land in the state, province, or region)
- major important agronomic traits (gall midge resistance, grain quality, etc.)

NEWEST RICE VARIETIES, released by each station over the past 10 years.

Include the following information:

- varietal name
- source of variety
- previous line designation
- cross (if of hybrid origin) or progenitor (if pureline selection or mutant) from which the variety was selected
- plant height
- growth duration (days from seed to seed)
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture for which recommended (rainfed lowland, deep water, etc.)
- state, province, or region (political) where released
- estimate of the area on which the variety is grown (both total number of hectares and percent of total rice land in the state, province, or region)
- important agronomic traits

ELITE BREEDING LINES, the most promising prerelease lines in advanced yield trials of the ultimate stage of testing (on-station, regional, minikit, or production trials). Will probably be no more than 10 lines/geographic region.

Please provide information on:

- line designation
- cross from which the line was selected
- plant height
- growth duration
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture for which intended
- important agronomic traits
- state, province, or region (political)

HYBRIDIZATION OR CROSSING

RECORDS, made since the initiation of crossbreeding at various stations. Anyone who has access to old crossing records from programs that no longer exist is also requested to provide a copy so that the ancestry of varieties that came from those crosses will not be lost to future generations. Include:

- name of station and country
- line designation (K, BR, etc.) and number
- cross (female parent first, then male)
- year (approx.) that cross was made

The information should be sent to:

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Associate Editor
International Rice Research
Institute
P. O. Box 933
Manila, Philippines

Thank you in advance for your time and consideration.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Germplasm conservation

Primitive cultivated rices and wild relatives from the Chhotanagpur region of southern Bihar, India

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The hilly, rainfed Chhotanagpur region of southern Bihar is predominantly

inhabited by tribal people. The terraced lands vary widely in ecological and agronomic systems, ranging from moisture-stressed upland conditions to wet lowland conditions. On the basis of moisture and water regimes the lands are classified into six groups: Tanr 1, Tanr 2, Tanr 3, Don 3, Don 2, and Don 1. The Tanr lands are subject to moisture stress, which is most severe in Tanr 1 followed by that in Tanr 2 and 3. Don 1 lands are waterlogged throughout the cropping season, while Don 3 and 2 depend on rainfall for moisture.

A rich variability of cultivated rice is found in those systems. Annual and perennial wild rices of the *O. sativa* type are also common. The Gora rices (early

maturing) are grown in Tanr lands in Ranchi district. The well-known Black Gora has primitive characteristics, i.e., black hulls and red kernels. Annual wild rices (similar to *O. nivara*) are also frequently observed in the fields of Black Gora. They have black hulls, red kernels, and awned spikelets. Their grains tend to shatter. The wild rices show some similarities to Black Gora.

In Chaibasa district, annual wild rices, some with black and others with straw hulls, are found near rice fields. Semisterile annual wild rices that appear to be hybrids with *O. sativa* are also common in some regions. A few cultivated rices such as Chidikata, Koya, and Kosambaba have certain characters

similar to those of annual wild rices - black hulls, awns, and red kernels. Kosambaba has both straw and black hulls. In one instance, Chidikata was observed with black as well as with golden brown hulls. A few varieties also had intravarietal variations.

Such rices as Black Gora, Chidikata, Koya, and Kosambaba that the tribal people cultivate appear to be primitive cultivars with many of the characters of their nearby wild relatives. Such varieties could be valuable in understanding genetic interrelationships; they could offer opportunities for the study of the affinity of the cultivated rices and their adjoining wild relatives. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Hardness and stickiness of cooked rice as indicators of eating quality

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Methods of measuring stickiness and hardness of cooked rice with an Instron food tester were developed using 20 g raw milled rice cooked in an optimum amount of water based on amylose content. Stickiness was measured as the work required to separate the plunger from the platform with cooked rice pressed between them. Hardness was the maximum force required to extrude the cooked rice through a modified Ottawa Texture Measuring System extrusion cell. Both stickiness and hardness of cooked rice, mostly IRRI samples, correlated with amylose content (see figure). But the hardness values varied more than stickiness values for all amylose levels.

Among IRRI high-amylose (>25%) rices, the grain of those with soft gel consistency tends to be softer and more sticky when cooked. Varietal differences in texture among rices with low or intermediate amylose content were associated with differences in hardness

Relationship between amylose content of milled rice and Instron stickiness and hardness of rice cooked with the optimum level of water and then cooled. IRRI, 1977.

of cooked rice rather than with differences in stickiness. Among Philippine and Indonesian rices of intermediate amylose content (20–25%), samples with soft gel consistency and low amylograph consistency tended to be soft when cooked. In some cases, differences in hardness of cooked rice were associated with differences in gelatinization temperature of the starch (alkali spreading value). Among South Korean and Japanese low-amylose (12–20%) rices, hardness values of cooked rice were related mainly to differences in gel and amylograph consistency. When cooked, the preferred waxy varieties from Korea, Philippines, and Thailand were soft and sticky, and tended to have low (<70°C) gelatinization temperature. ❧

Properties of lintnerized starch granules from rices of different amylose content and gelatinization temperature

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The gelatinization temperature of starch is rapidly becoming recognized as an important indicator of eating quality of both waxy (glutinous) and nonwaxy rices. Its measurement in breeding programs by